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Mediation analysis of antidepressant use, depressive symptoms, and recurrent falls in community-dwelling older fallers: An exploratory study

Adson da Silva Passos, PhD^{a,b,c,*}, Adriana Sanudo, PhD^{a,d}, Érika Yukie Ishigaki, MSc^{a,e}, Maria Aquimara Zambone Magalhães, MSc^{a,f}, Silvana Barbosa Pena, PhD^{a,g}, Andreia Cristina Feitosa do Carmo, MSc^h, Sérgio Márcio Pacheco Paschoal, PhD^a, Monica Rodrigues Perracini, PhD^{a,i,j}, Luiz Eugênio Garcez Leme, PhD^{a,b}

^a *PrevQuedas Brazil Research Group, Faculty of Medicine, Universidade de São Paulo, Rua Dr. Ovídio Pires de Campos, 333, Cerqueira Cesar, Zip code:05403-010, São Paulo, Brazil*

^b *Institute of Orthopedics and Traumatology, Faculty of Medicine, Universidade de São Paulo, Rua Dr. Ovídio Pires de Campos, 333, Cerqueira Cesar, Zip code: 05403-010, São Paulo, Brazil*

^c *Faculty of Medicine, Universidade Paulista, Av. Independência, 210, Éden, Zip code: 18087-101, Sorocaba, Brazil*

^d *Department of Preventive Medicine, Universidade Federal de São Paulo, Rua Botucatu, 740, Zip code: 04023-062, São Paulo, Brazil*

^e *Centro Universitário Faculdade de Medicina do ABC, Avenida Lauro Gomes, 2000, Zip code:09060-870, Santo André, Brazil*

^f *Department of Nutrition, Hospital das Clínicas da Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de São Paulo, Rua. Dr. Ovídio Pires de Campos, 225, Cerqueira César, Zip code: 05403-010, São Paulo, Brazil*

^g *Faculty of Nursing, Universidade Federal do Mato grosso do Sul, Av. Ranulpho Marques Leal, 3484, Zip code: 79613-000, Três Lagoas, Brazil*

^h *Biblioteca do Campus São Paulo, Universidade Federal de São Paulo, Rua Botucatu, 740, Zip code: 04023-062, São Paulo, Brazil*

ⁱ *Master's and Doctoral Programs in Physical Therapy, Rua Cesareo Galeno, 448, Zip code: 03071-000, São Paulo, Brazil*

^j *Master's and Doctoral Programs in Gerontology, Rua Tessalia Vieira de Camargo, 126, Zip code: 13083-887, Campinas, Brazil*

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aimed to explore whether there might exist an interaction between using antidepressants and the influence of depressive symptoms on the recurrence of falls.

Design: Cross-sectional study using secondary data from a randomized clinical trial.

Setting and participants: Community-dwelling older adults ($n = 609$, aged 73.4 ± 7.4 years) who had experienced at least one fall in the past 12 months.

Methods: Depressive symptoms were measured using the Geriatric Depression Scale, and information about antidepressant usage was collected. Mediation models were built to decompose the effects of depressive symptoms on fall risk into direct effects and indirect effects mediated by antidepressant use.

Results: Depressive symptoms were reported by 29.1 % of the participants, and 27.4 % were using antidepressants. Those with depressive symptoms had 1.86 times the likelihood of being recurrent fallers ($OR_{TE}: 1.861$, 95 % CI: 1.197, 2.895), and there was no significant interaction between depressive symptoms and antidepressant use on recurrent falls ($P_{interaction} = 0.989$). Antidepressant use might be a significant mediator in the relationship between depressive symptoms and recurrent falls ($OR_{NIE}: 1.140$, 95 % CI: 1.007, 1.291), accounting for 21.1 % of the total effect.

Conclusions/implications: Antidepressants probably do not add a significant risk of recurrent falls beyond what is already contributed by the presence of depressive symptoms. A longitudinal study could clarify whether it might be safe to use antidepressants to treat older people with depressive symptoms without increasing the risk of falls the disease leads by itself.

* Corresponding author at: Rua Paulo Antonio do Nascimento, 145, sala 133. Jardim Portal da Colina. Sorocaba, Zip code: 03071-000, São Paulo, Brazil.

E-mail address: dr_adson@yahoo.com.br (A.S. Passos).

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1. Introduction

A fall represents a life-changing event for older adults that results in adverse physical and mental health problems, regardless of whether it caused a severe injury (Hartley et al., 2023). One-third of the older adults, 65 years and older, experience falls yearly, and half are recurrent fallers who frequently need medical attention and are at significant risk of being admitted to a long-term care facility (Iaboni and Flint, 2013). Fall-related costs can reach \$50 billion annually, representing a high global burden for healthcare systems, and they will increase dramatically in low-middle-income countries due to the rapid population aging (Florence et al., 2018).

Several cumulative, interrelated risk factors and underlying health conditions contribute to recurrent falls, unveiling a complex care condition (Iaboni and Flint, 2013). Depression is present in approximately 45 % of older people who suffer recurrent falls (Launay et al., 2013), and it can be a pre-existing condition or a fall-related consequence (Choi et al., 2019). The interplay between depression or depressive symptoms and the use of antidepressants can significantly limit older people's mobility and engagement in physical and social activities, increasing the likelihood of falling due to deconditioning (Belloni et al., 2020; Iaboni and Flint, 2013; van Poelgeest et al., 2021). Furthermore, depression can negatively affect executive functions related to attentional and regulatory mechanisms crucial for maintaining balance and safe walking (Patience et al., 2019).

Depressive symptoms have been recognized as a fall risk factor and might catalyze the risk of falling regardless of using antidepressants. However, antidepressants have been systematically included in the list of fall-risk-increasing drugs (FRIDs) (Seppala et al., 2021). They are prescribed for various reasons, including but not limited to treating depression, anxiety, neuropathic pain, and urinary incontinence. Several studies have demonstrated an association between the use of antidepressants and single and recurrent falls in older people (Haddad et al., 2021; Park et al., 2015; Quach et al., 2013; van Poelgeest et al., 2021). Different classes of antidepressants have been linked to recurrent falls (Haddad et al., 2021; Sobieraj et al., 2019). Given that there is evidence indicating that depressive symptoms and the use of antidepressants are potentially modifiable risk factors for falls among older people and that their interplay is still unclear (Prizer et al., 2016), identifying their impact in determining falls is crucial. We sought to explore whether there might exist an interaction between using antidepressants and depressive symptoms on the recurrence of falls.

2. Methods

2.1. Setting

We analyzed the baseline data “PrevQuedas Brazil (a multicenter controlled trial seeking to evaluate the efficacy of a multifactorial falls prevention intervention composed of individualized risk factor management, exercise, and educational/behavior change sessions in reducing fall rates in community-dwelling older adults living in Brazil, when compared to usual care) (De Negreiros Cabral et al., 2013). Participants were enrolled in various settings (senior care centers, primary care centers, and hospitals) from March 2014 to August 2019. They were evaluated by a multidisciplinary team trained to conduct interviews, clinical examinations, and physical functioning tests. Clinical trial registration number: NCT01698580 (De Negreiros Cabral et al., 2013).

2.2. Participants

We included 609 participants aged 60 years and over who had fallen at least once in the past 12 months. We excluded three participants from the total of 612 due to missing information on the GDS-15 score. We defined falls as ‘any fall, slip or trip in which you lose your balance and land on the floor or ground or at a lower level’ (De Negreiros Cabral

et al., 2013). We excluded older people with severe visual or cognitive impairment or acute or chronic health conditions that could prevent them from exercising. They could not be engaged in any regular physical activity program twice a week or more. A detailed description of the clinical trial exclusion criteria was published elsewhere (De Negreiros Cabral et al., 2013).

2.3. Ethics

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from The Human Ethics Committee of the University of Sao Paulo - School of Medicine (protocol number: 0145/11). All participants provided written informed consent.

2.4. Measures

2.4.1. Sociodemographic variables

Sex (male, female), age (years), ethnicity/skin color (white, black, pardo, East Asian, and indigenous), living alone, educational level (illiterate, 1–4 years; 5–8 years and ≥ 9 years) and income (0–3 and > 3 minimum wages).

2.4.2. Health Condition variables

Body mass index (BMI) was measured in kg/m^2 and categorized as follows: low weight < 22 ; eutrophic between 22 and 27; overweight/obese > 27 (Lipschitz, 1994). Participants were divided into two groups according to the Charlson Comorbidity Index (low risk: 0–2 points, high/intermediate risk: > 2 points) (Charlson et al., 1987; Fuchs Bahlis et al., 2021). Global Cognition was assessed using the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) with a cutoff point of < 24 points used to determine a positive screening for cognitive decline (Folstein et al., 1975; Brucki et al., 2003). Fear of falling was assessed by asking, “Are you afraid of falling again?” (no/yes). Participants who responded positively were considered fearful of falling. (Belloni et al., 2020).

2.4.3. Physical-functional variables

The gait speed test was measured using a walking pathway of 4.6 m and the time in seconds to cover it. The cutoff of < 1.0 m/s (Adam et al., 2023) was used to identify participants with slow gait speed. Walking aids could be used.

2.4.4. Exposure/mediator/outcome variables

The exposure variable was the presence of depressive symptoms using the 15-item Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS). Older people taking GDS-15 ≥ 6 points were considered to have depressive symptoms (Yesavage et al., 1982; Almeida and Almeida, 1999). Participants taking GDS-15 between 6 to 10 and 11 to 15 were classified as having mild and moderate/severe depressive symptoms, respectively (Brasil, 2007). Antidepressant use (yes/no) was considered a mediator. Older people were interviewed by healthcare professionals (doctors, nurses, and other allied health professionals) and instructed to bring their medical prescriptions and a list of medications regularly used (medicine packs). The outcome variable was the number of falls in the past 12 months (one or ≥ 2 events).

2.5. Analysis

Qualitative variables were described as numbers (n) and percentages (%). Pearson's chi-square test assessed all associations with the exposure variable. We first conducted a causal mediation analysis to allow for the identification and estimation of the indirect and direct effects of exposure on the outcome. We implemented mediation models using the Stata package “paramedic” to decompose the effects of depression on fall risk into direct effects and indirect effects mediated by antidepressant use. We estimated the natural direct effect (NDE), natural indirect effect (NIE), total effect (TE), and percent effect mediated (PEM) on the odds ratio scale using logistic regression adjusted for selected confounders. To

assess potential interaction effects between exposure (depression) and mediator (antidepressant use), we estimated a model with and without including an exposure-mediator interaction. Model covariate selection was guided by previous literature and directed acyclic graphs. Statistical analysis was conducted using Stata/SE 18 (Stata-Corp, 2023; College Station, TX: StataCorp LLC).

2.5.1. Sensitivity analysis

We assessed the robustness of the reported associations to potential unmeasured and uncontrolled confounding. We used the E-Value measure, defined as the minimum strength of association on the odds ratio scale that a missing confounder would need to have with both the exposure and outcome variables to explain away the exposure-outcome association completely (Van Der Weele and Ding, 2017).

3. Results

The study recruited 609 participants, mean age (standard deviation) of 73.4 (7.4) years, ranging from 60 to 100. Recurrent fallers were 68 % (95 %CI: 64.1–71.7) of the participants. Depressive symptoms (GDS-15 ≥ 6 points) were found in 29.1 % of the sample (177 persons). Of these, 4.9 % had severe depressive symptoms (GDS-15 ≥ 11). We did not find a significant association between GDS-15 categories (mild/severe) and the number of falls ($p=0.830$).

Table 1 presents the characteristics of the participants stratified according to depressive symptoms presence. Significant differences according to this stratification were: low education level, monthly income ≤ 3 minimum wages, the use of walking aids, being classified as ‘at risk’ in the Charlson Comorbidity Index, MMSE <24 points, being afraid of falling again, using antidepressants, and gait speed <1 m/s. Approximately 27.4 % of the participants answered that they were using antidepressants, and among these, the most frequent classes used were SSRIs and tricyclics (76.5 % and 15.1 %, respectively). Some participants used antidepressants, antidepressants with other psychoactive medication, and only psychoactive medication other than antidepressants. The psychoactive medication most used, besides antidepressants, were hypnotics (alprazolam, bromazepam, clonazepam, cloxazolam, diazepam, lorazepam and zolpidem); anticonvulsants (carbamazepine, gabapentin, lamotrigine, pregabalin and topiramate); and antipsychotics (quetiapine and periciazine).

A model estimate considering depressive symptoms as a primary exposure is displayed in Table 2. A comparison of model estimates and tests of statistical significance revealed no significant exposure-mediator interaction (P interaction = 0.989); therefore, we only presented the model estimates assuming no exposure-mediator interaction. After adjusting for potential exposure-outcome, exposure-mediator, and mediator-outcome confounders, our results revealed that people who had GDS-15 ≥ 6 points presented 1.86 times the chance of being a recurrent faller (OR_{TE} : 1.861, 95 %CI: 1.197, 2.895). The use of antidepressants might be a significant mediator of the association between depressive symptoms and recurrent falls (OR_{NIE} : 1.140, 95 %CI: 1.007, 1.291), equating to 21.1 % of the total effect.

Sensitivity analysis using E-values suggested that the observed associations were at least moderately robust to potential unmeasured confounding since the E-value for NDE was 2.85, with a lower bound of the confidence interval equal to 1.29. These results indicated that an unmeasured confounding variable would require an association of at least $OR = 1.29$ with recurrent falls and antidepressive symptoms to nullify the observed associations.

4. Discussion

Our results showed antidepressants could probably mediate depressive symptoms and recurrent falls. However, no significant interaction between depressive symptoms (exposure) and antidepressants (mediator) was observed, meaning that there might not exist an additional risk

Table 1

Characteristics of the sample and its association with depressive symptoms among community-dwelling older fallers. Data from PrevQuedas Brazil ($n=609$).

	Total ($n=609$)	Depressive Symptoms		p-value
		GDS ≥ 6 ($n=177$)	GDS < 6 ($n=432$)	
Sociodemographic				
Sex				
Male	82 (13.5 %)	18 (10.2 %)	64 (14.8 %)	0.127
Female	527 (86.5 %)	159 (89.8 %)	368 (85.2 %)	
Age, years				
60 – 75	371 (60.9 %)	11 (62.7 %)	260 (60.2 %)	0.562
> 75	238 (39.1 %)	66 (37.3 %)	172 (39.8 %)	
Race/ Ethnicity				
White	368 (60.4 %)	98 (55.4 %)	270 (62.5 %)	0.062
Black	55 (9.0 %)	19 (10.7 %)	36 (8.3 %)	
Pardo	130 (21.4 %)	48 (27.1 %)	82 (19.0 %)	
East Asian/ Indigenous	56 (9.2 %)	12 (6.8 %)	44 (10.2 %)	
Educational level (years)				
Illiterate	32 (5.3 %)	11 (6.2 %)	21 (4.7 %)	0.002
Low (1–4)	249 (40.9 %)	91 (51.4 %)	158 (36.6 %)	
Medium (5–8)	133 (21.8 %)	36 (20.4 %)	97 (22.5 %)	
High (≥ 9)	195 (32.0 %)	39 (22.0 %)	156 (36.1 %)	
Income				
0 – 3 MW	505 (83.2 %)	162 (92.1 %)	343 (79.6 %)	< 0.001
> 3 MW	102 (16.8 %)	14 (7.9 %)	88 (20.4 %)	
Living Alone				
	95 (15.6 %)	32 (18.1 %)	63 (14.6 %)	0.280
Health Conditions				
Charlson				
Low risk	509 (83.6 %)	139 (78.5 %)	370 (85.6 %)	0.031
Risk	100 (16.4 %)	38 (21.5 %)	62 (14.4 %)	
BMI				
Low weight	43 (7.1 %)	9 (5.1 %)	34 (7.9 %)	0.201
Eutrophic	209 (34.4 %)	55 (31.3 %)	154 (35.7 %)	
Overweight/ Obese	355 (58.5 %)	112 (63.6 %)	243 (56.4 %)	
Mini-Mental				
≥ 24 points	497 (81.6 %)	131 (74.0 %)	366 (84.7 %)	0.002
< 24 points	112 (18.4 %)	46 (26.0 %)	66 (15.3 %)	
Fear of Falling again				
	475 (78.0 %)	155 (87.6 %)	320 (74.1 %)	< 0.001
Psychoactive medication				
Antidepressive only	139 (67.8 %)	61 (68.5 %)	78 (67.2 %)	0.941
Antidepressive and other psychoactive medication	32 (15.6 %)	13 (14.6 %)	19 (16.4 %)	
Other psychoactive medication only	34 (16.6 %)	15 (16.9 %)	19 (16.4 %)	
Outcome/ mediator				
Recurrent falls				
	414 (68.0 %)	139 (78.5 %)	275 (63.7 %)	< 0.001
Antidepressive use				
	171 (28.1 %)	74 (41.8 %)	97 (22.5 %)	< 0.001
Antidepressive classes				
				0.680

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

	Total (n=609)	Depressive Symptoms		p- value
		GDS ≥ 6 (n=177)	GDS < 6 (n=432)	
SSRIs	132 (77.2 %)	56 (75.7 %)	76 (78.4 %)	
Others	39 (22.8 %)	18 (24.3 %)	21 (21.6 %)	
Physical-functional				
Gait speed				0.010
≥ 1.0 m/s	335 (55.0 %)	83 (46.9 %)	252 (58.3 %)	
< 1.0 m/s	274 (45.0 %)	94 (53.1 %)	180 (41.7 %)	
Use of walking aids	85 (14.0 %)	34 (19.2 %)	51 (11.8 %)	0.017

MW, Monthly wage; BMI, Body Mass Index

Table 2

Direct and indirect effects of depressive symptoms on recurrent falls.

Mediator		OR	95 % CI	p-value
Use of AD	NDE	1.632	1.053 – 2.531	0.029
	NIE	1.140	1.007 – 1.291	0.038
	TE	1.861	1.197 – 2.895	0.006
	PEM*	0.211		

Model was adjusted for age, race, educational attainment, income, living alone, use of walking aids, Charlson Comorbidity Index, BMI, MMSE, Fear of falling, and speed gait.

AD, antidepressant medication; NDE, natural direct effect; NIE, natural indirect effect; TE, Total Effect; OR, odds ratio; PEM, percent effect mediated.

* calculated on log odds scale: $\log\text{NIE}/\log\text{TE}$

of falling when treating patients with depressive symptoms.

Evidence shows that using antidepressant medications in older people, particularly tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs), can lead to falls by increasing some adverse outcomes such as cardiovascular events (e.g., postural hypotension) due to age-related changes in pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics (Sultana et al., 2015). However, the safety of using SSRIs is still controversial, and the exact mechanisms are unclear (Marcum et al., 2016).

Quach et al. identified a 67 % greater incidence of falls among older adults with clinically significant depressive symptoms (CSDS) that could be mediated by antidepressant use. However, antidepressants' indirect effect was not analyzed (Quach et al., 2013).

Several guidelines, such as the 2023 updated AGS Beers Criteria® and the STOPFALL®, have been created to help clinicians find a safer way to treat older patients (Seppala et al., 2021; By the 2023 American Geriatrics Society Beers Criteria® Update Expert Panel, 2023). According to the American Geriatrics Society's 2023 updated AGS Beers Criteria® for potentially inappropriate medication use in older adults, antidepressants like tricyclics (TCAs), serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs), and selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) should be avoided in patients with a history of falls and fractures unless safer alternatives are not available (By the 2023 American Geriatrics Society Beers Criteria® Update Expert Panel, 2023). Sobieraj et al. found that SNRIs, but not SSRIs, were associated with more overall adverse events (versus placebo) when treating depression. Duloxetine was found to increase the number of falls (Sobieraj et al., 2019). Recently, the World guidelines for falls recommended that medication review and appropriate deprescribing of FRIDs should be part of multidomain falls prevention interventions (Montero-Odasso et al., 2022).

An existing bidirectional relationship between major depression and depressive symptoms and their association with falls has been studied (Choi et al., 2019). Patients with depressive symptoms are more likely to experience recurrent falls, and they are also more likely to develop

depressive symptoms after falling again. The rationale for using antidepressants should balance benefits and risks. Its use should not imply a greater risk of falling than the underlying condition (depression). If this was the case, using antidepressants, particularly in frail older people, could be more harmful. On the other hand, not treating depressive symptoms might have a substantial adverse impact on the health of older people, including premature mortality (Lenze and Ajam Oughli, 2019). Untreated depression worsens quality of life, may lead to misdiagnosis of dementia (Voros et al., 2020), and increases the likelihood of falls (van Poelgeest et al., 2021).

Our results showed that the likelihood of recurrent falls determined by the presence of depressive symptoms was higher than the mediated effect using antidepressants, controlling for confounders as demonstrated once by Lohman et al (Lohman et al., 2021). The effect of depressive symptoms on recurrent falls before mediation analysis is called the total effect. After mediation analysis, this total effect is decomposed into two categories: the NDE (effect of depressive symptoms on recurrent falls controlled by antidepressant use) and the NIE (effect of depressive symptoms on recurrent falls mediated by antidepressant use). After adjustment for confounders, the participation of antidepressants in the likelihood of recurrent falls (PEM) is 22.1 %, and the participation of depressive symptoms is 78.9 % (Fig. 1).

These numbers demonstrate that it might be safe to use antidepressants to treat older people with depressive symptoms without increasing the risk of falls the disease leads. This may encourage clinicians not to leave their older patients who are at risk of falling without treatment for clinically significant depressive symptoms.

4.1. Strengths and limitations

This study has some limitations. First, information on the use of antidepressants was based on self-report, which could have led to recall bias. We have tried to obtain accurate information on regularly used medications, asking participants to bring their prescriptions, pill boxes, and packs and even making phone calls to their caregivers to check the information. Second, we have decided to group antidepressants as a dichotomous variable rather than categorizing them into subclasses due to the small number of participants using classes other than SSRIs. In our country, the Public Healthcare System offers SSRI as the primary free-of-charge class of antidepressants to treat depression, followed by TCAs. We also did not have accurate access to antidepressant dosage information, and this could be an unmeasured confounding factor influencing the relationships examined. Third, we were not able to check with participants' primary care physicians about the clinical diagnostic of depression based on DSM-V criteria and if the use of antidepressants was for treating depression or other comorbidities. In the same way, although participants self-reported a diagnosis of depression, we decided only to use depressive symptoms evaluated by GDS as the exposure. We tried to differentiate participants into having mild depressive symptoms (GDS-15 = 6–10 points) and moderate/severe depressive symptoms (GDS-15 = 11–15points), but there was a small number of individuals with severe scores (4.9 %), and we did not find a significant difference between these categories and the number of falls. Fourth, our sample was limited to community-dwelling older adults with a history of falls, so the interpretation of the results should be limited to the same situation. Fifth, mediation analysis in cross-sectional studies has some limitations, primarily due to the assumption of temporal precedence. Due to the lack of temporal information, such studies struggle to account for unmeasured confounding variables that might influence the relationships studied. The percentage of mediation should be interpreted cautiously as it may not represent an actual causal mediation process but rather the proportion of the association between depressive symptoms and recurrent falls that is statistically accounted for by antidepressant use. Therefore, findings from cross-sectional mediation analyses should be interpreted as exploratory or correlational, not definitive evidence of a causal process. While sensitivity analyses can

Fig. 1. Mediation Analyses after adjustment for potential confounders showing the direct effect of depressive symptoms and the indirect effect of antidepressant use on recurrent falls in community-dwelling older adults. PEM, percent effect mediated.

help assess the robustness of mediation conclusions, longitudinal or experimental designs that establish temporal precedence are ideal for testing causal mediation processes.

Our study design was cross-sectional, and falls were based on self-report, potentially leading to a recall bias. Furthermore, the nature of the study design limits the ability to make strong clinical recommendations.

5. Conclusions

Possibly, it might be worth using antidepressants to treat older people who have depressive symptoms and are at greater risk of recurrent falling since the mediated effect of antidepressants is lower than the effect induced by depressive symptoms. A cohort study should further confirm our results. The use of antidepressants is one of the most effective ways to treat depression, resulting in a better quality of life for older people.

Disclosures

This paper was not submitted or presented at a meeting and has not been published as a preprint.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Adson da Silva Passos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Adriana Sanudo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Érika Yukie Ishigaki:** Resources, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maria Aquimara Zambone Magalhães:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Silvana Barbosa**

Pena: Writing – review & editing, Resources, Conceptualization. **Andreia Cristina Feitosa do Carmo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Sérgio Márcio Pacheco Paschoal:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Monica Rodrigues Perracini:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Luiz Eugênio Garcez Leme:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Monica Rodrigues Perracini reports financial support was provided by State of Sao Paulo Research Foundation. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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